

Intervention of viral infections by targeting host cellular protease : A proposition based on viral glycoprotein processing[†]

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Abstract : During the past century our world has witnessed a number of global pandemic outbreaks of viral infections from time to time, often with deadly consequences. However, in recent years viral infections of new types or variants are beginning to emerge often with significantly high virulence properties. A number of these new strains are derived from animals such as avian, cattle, primates, etc. which have crossed the animal barrier due to varying reasons that may include the change in lifestyle, food habit, increased migration, globalization as well as living and staying too close to animals. Extensive research has been undertaken to better understand the genetic and protein architectures of these and other highly infectious viruses and their mode of progression. Already potential targets have been identified for development of safe and effective intervention and treatment strategies. *These are all directed towards the viral components such as viral enzyme, viral protein and viral membrane associated with the fusiogenic event.* However, host cellular enzyme/s of protease family also plays a critical role in viral pathogenesis and infection. It cleaves viral surface glycoproteins leading to their maturation forms to be recognized by host cellular receptor. This leads to viral fusion with host membrane and delivery of its components leading to viral replication and progression. As a result, these selected host proteases may also be considered as important targets for blockade of viral infection and pathogenesis. In this respect, one enzyme in particular called furin (also known as PCSK3) that belongs to the Proprotein Convertase Subtilisin Kexin (PCSK) super family stands out the most. In fact, furin inhibitors have been developed and shown *in vitro* and animal models to diminish viral replication and its load. Development of highly selective furin inhibitors is thus an attractive option to fight against the viral infections despite the challenge one has to face in terms of enzyme specificity, potency and delivery of anti-furin agents in an organ/tissue-specific manner. This review discusses the various issues facing this approach. Both pros and cons of this methodology are discussed and debated in this review.

Keywords : Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), corona virus, ebola virus, chikungunya virus, dengue virus, respiratory syncytial virus, viral surface glycoproteins, protein processing, viral intervention, host cellular protease, furin, proprotein convertase, proprotein convertase subtilisin kexin, protease inhibitors.

Background

In recent years we have seen the emergence and re-emergence of a variety of infectious diseases throughout the world. These were caused mostly by viruses of different class types and strains with high virulence property. Unlike in ancient times, nowadays such infections are not necessarily contained in one particular location of the world where they originate. Instead, they can spread to other regions rapidly as a result of increased human air travel and migration. The intensification of farming, hus-

bandry, increased activity with exotic and other animals as well as global warming are some of the other factors which may have contributed as well^{1,2}. Frequently it was observed that a virus unknown to human and only contained within specific animals, has crossed into the humans with increased virulence. In most cases, it was also noted that the viral genome underwent mutations (change of one or more nucleic acids) while invading the humans leading to enhanced pathogenesis and rapid progression^{3,4}. Some typical examples of these class of viruses are AIDS

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

(Acquired Immuno Deficiency Syndrome) caused by human immune-deficiency virus (HIV), SARS (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome) caused by human SARS corona virus, Ebola infections (caused by Ebola virus), Avian Bird flu (caused by H5N1), Swine flu (caused by H1N1 virus), Chikungunya fever (caused by mosquito-borne Alpha viruses), etc. These virus particles or viroid as they are often termed are described by their highly characteristic features and morphology as observed in high resolution microscope. Depending on the nature, these highly contagious particles which can multiply quite rapidly can travel via air, physical contact, biological or body fluid and can infect other individuals, who are quite healthy otherwise. Therefore, the containment of these viruses is extremely vital for their blockade they can spread very rapidly infecting other population who are otherwise healthy. Owing to their enormous importance and global interest, we thought that a review article in this field highlighting various possible targets including the host protease/s will be extremely valuable to the research and scientific community.

Past pandemics

During the entire history of human civilization, many global pandemics caused by highly infectious particles like virus or bacteria have been documented in the literature. A list of known world pandemics so far recorded in the literature with major historical impact is shown in Table 1. These had serious consequences worldwide with huge loss of human lives bringing fear and helplessness among the general population. Yet the mankind somehow managed to overcome these setbacks and contained the infections as much as possible. Some of these events, particularly those which made historical impact on human life, growth and advancement, are listed in Tables 2a-2e (information taken from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pandemic>). These tables documented all the known global pandemics since the early AD to modern times that led to significant human death and destruction worldwide. The number one causative agent is the virus and plague that can infect a large population in a short period of time with deadly consequence. Tables 2a-2e indicated those pandemics appeared from time to time at various corners of the world which in most cases were not confined within the boundary of specific country, region or community. Improvements of public health awareness and method of containments are obviously needed to fight against the

Table 1. Known recorded world pandemics and the year of occurrence (Taken from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pandemic>)

Number	Year	Name of the pandemic
1	165-180	Antonine plague, perhaps smallpox
2	541	The plague of Justinian
3	1300's	The black death
4	1501-1587	Typhus
5	1732-1733	Influenza
6	1775-1776	Influenza
7	1816-1826	Cholera
8	1829-1851	Cholera
9	1847-1848	Influenza
10	1852-1860	Cholera
11	1855-1950's	Bubonic plague, Third pandemic
12	1857-1859	Influenza
13	1863-1875	Cholera
14	1889-1892	Influenza
15	1899-1923	Cholera
16	1918-1920	Avian (Spanish) flu, 20-100 million deaths
17	1960's	Cholera called E1 Tor
18	1980's	HIV (AIDS)
19	1997/2005	Bird flu (Hong Kong virus)
20	2003 -	h (human) SARS corona virus
21	2005 -	Ebola virus
22	2008 -	H1N1

Table 2a. List of important regional pandemics reported in Asia, the year of occurrence and the name of the country involved (Taken from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pandemic>)

Year	Type of pandemic infection	Place, Country
1334	Black death	China
1347	Black death	Anatolia
1349	Black death	Mecca, Saudi Arabia
1353-1354	Black death	China
1560	Plague	Istanbul, Turkey
1812	Plague	Istanbul, Turkey
1829-1835	Plague	Persia, Iran
1903	Plague	India
1957-1958	Avian influenza	Asian flu
1968-1969	Avian influenza	Hong Kong
1994	Bubonic plague	India
1997	Avian influenza,	Hong Kong, China
2002-2003	hSARS corona virus	China
2004	Dengue fever	Indonesia
2004	Cholera	Bangladesh
2004	Leishmaniasis	Afghanistan

Table-2a (contd.)

Table-2b (contd.)

2006	Malaria	India	1800-1803	Yellow fever	Spain
2006	Dengue fever	India	1813	Plague	Bucharest, Romania
2006	Dengue fever	Philippines	1816-1819	Typhus	Ireland
2006	Dengue fever	Pakistan	1821	Yellow fever	Barcelona, Spain
2006	Chikungunya	India	1832	Cholera	London, Paris
2007	Cholera	Iraq	1857	Yellow fever	Lisbon, Portugal
2007	Cholera	India	1866-1867	Cholera	Russia/Germany
2007	Cholera	Vietnam	1870-1871	Smallpox	Germany
2008	Dengue fever	Cambodia	1881-1896	Cholera	Hamburg, Germany
2008	Hand, foot and mouth disease	China	1918-1922	Typhus	Russia
2008	Dengue fever	Philippines	1972	Smallpox	Yugoslavia

Table 2b. List of important regional pandemics in **Europe**, the years of their occurrences and the name of the country involved

Year	Type of pandemic infection	Place, Country
1347-1351	Black death	Plague, Czech
1428	Black death	London, England
1466	Plague	Paris, France
1489	Typhus	Grenada, Spain
1485	Sweating sickness	UK
1494-1495	Plague	Iceland
1498	Plague	England
1509-1510	Plague	England
1527	Plague	Germany
1557	Plague	Valencia, Spain
1563-1564	Plague	England
1570	Plague	Moscow, Russia
1574	Plague	Scotland, Edinburgh
1596-1602	Plague	Spain
1603	Plague	London, England
1630	Great Plague	Milan, Italy
1630-1631	Plague	Venice, Italy
1636	Plague	Newcastle, UK
1647-1652	Plague	Seville, Spain
1656	Plague	Naples, Italy
1663-1664	Plague, Amstardam	Netherland
1665	Great plague	London, UK
1668	Plague	France
1676-1685	Plague	Spain
1679	Plague of Vienna	Austria
1710-1711	Plague	Stockholm, Sweden
1720-1722	Plague	Marseille, France
1730	Yellow fever	Cadiz, Spain
1743	Plague	Messina, Italy
1770-1772	Plague	Russia
1778	Dengue fever	Cadiz, Spain

Table 2c. List of regional pandemics in **Australia and New Zealand**, the year of occurrence and the name of the country involved

1789-1790	Smallpox	Aboroginals, New South Wells
1828	Smallpox	Aboroginals, New South Wells
1829	Smallpox	South Australia
1857	Smallpox	Victoria, Australia
1867	Measles	Sydney, Australia

Table 2d. List of reported regional pandemics in **Central and South America**, the year of occurrence and the name of the country involved

1493	Influenza	Hispaniola
1507	Smallpox	Hispaniola
1527-1530	Smallpox	Mexico
1530-1531	Measles	Mexico and Peru
1546	Typhus	Mexico/Peru
1555	Smallpox	Brazil
1558-1559	Influenza	South America
1561	Smallpox	Chile
1576	Haemorrhagic fever	Mexico
Early 1600s	Malaria	Global
1648	Yellow fever	Global
1980-present	AIDS	Haiti, Global
1990's	Cholera	Global
2000	Dengue	Central America
2007	Dengue	Puerto Rico and Democratic Republic of Congo
2008	Dengue	Brazil

Table 2e. List of reported regional pandemics in **North America**, the year of occurrence and the name of the country involved

1592-1596	Measles	North America and Global
1617-1619	Smallpox	Mass, USA
1630	Smallpox	Huron, USA and Canada
1634	Smallpox	Indians, Connecticut, USA

Table-2e (contd.)

Table-2e (contd.)

1633	Smallpox	Plymouth, USA	1855	Yellow fever	USA
1657	Measles	Boston, Mass, USA	1860-1861	Smallpox	Pennsylvania, USA
1687	Measles	Boston, Mass, USA	1862	Smallpox	Pacific North West,
1690	Yellow fever	New York, USA			particularly the British
1713	Measles	Boston, Mass, USA			Columbia coast and
1713-1715	Measles	New England, USA			Interior, Canada
1729	Measles	Boston, Mass, USA	1865-1873	Smallpox	Philadelphia, NY City,
1738	Smallpox	South Carolina, USA			Boston and New Orleans,
1739-1740	Measles	Boston, Mass, USA			USA
1747	Measles	Connecticut, USA	1865-1873	Cholera	Baltimore, Memphis,
1755-1756	Smallpox	North America			Washington DC, USA
1759	Measles	North America	1865-1873	Recurring epidemics	USA
1761	Influenza	USA		of typhus, typhoid,	
1770's	Smallpox	North West Coast, USA		Scarlet Fever and	
1772	Measles	North America		Yellow fever	
1775	Unknown cause	North America			
1780-1782	Smallpox	Indian Plains, USA	1873-1875	Influenza	North America and Europe
1783	Bilious disorder	Dover, Delaware, USA	1876	Smallpox	Deadwood, South Dakota,
1788	Measles	Philadelphia, NY city, USA			USA
1788	Smallpox	Pueblo Indians, USA	1878	Yellow fever	Memphis, New Orleans,
1793	Influenza and "putrid fever"	Vermont, USA			USA
1793	Influenza	Virginia, USA	1885	Typhoid	Plymouth, Pennsylvania,
1793	Yellow fever	Philadelphia, Pa, USA			USA
1793	Unknown	Harrisburg, Pa, USA	1886	Yellow fever	Jacksonville, Florida, USA
1793	Unknown	Middletown, Pa, USA	1900-1904	"Third Pandemic"	San Francisco, USA
1794	Yellow fever	Philadelphia, Pa, USA	1918-1920	Spanish flu	USA, Canada, Mexico +
1796-1797	Yellow fever	Philadelphia, Pa, USA			Worldwide
1798	Yellow fever	Philadelphia, Pa, USA	1999-2003	West Nile Virus	USA and Canada
1803	Yellow fever	New York, USA	1980-present	HIV/AIDS	USA
1820-1823	Fever	USA			
1831-1832	Asiatic cholera	USA			
1831-1834	Smallpox	Plains Indians, USA			
1832	Cholera	New York/elsewhere, USA			
1833	Cholera	Columbus, Ohio, USA			
1834	Cholera	New York City, USA			
1837	Typhoid	Philadelphia, Pa, USA			
1837-1838	Smallpox	Great Plains, USA			
1841	Yellow fever	USA (especially severe in the South)			
1847	Yellow fever	New Orleans, USA			
1848-1849	Cholera	North America			
1849	Cholera	New York City, USA			
1850	Yellow fever	USA			
1850-1851	Influenza	North America			
1851	Cholera	Coles County, Illinois, USA			
1852	Yellow fever	USA (New Orleans, 8,000 deaths in summer)			

spread of these deadly infections. This is particularly applicable to underdeveloped or developing nations which were poor and heavily populated. Among all the viruses capable of infecting humans, **HIV** (Human Immune Deficiency Virus) which causes **AIDS** (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome) is one of the most feared and deadly ones. It is known to be transmitted via contact with body fluid of affected individual/s. Despite accumulated research and all the efforts, there is still no complete cure or effective treatment of AIDS. However with the advent of more sophisticated and modern antiviral treatments and instruments made available to affected population, the life span has improved dramatically. Thus, nowadays people are living a longer life with the disease more under control. Unfortunately in addition to AIDS, we are now facing with the problem of newly created variants of

viruses that often exhibit enhanced virulence and infection properties. Typical examples are human (h) **SARS corona**, **H5N1 (Hong Kong)**, **H1N1 (Swine flu)** and other new HN type viruses. As a result, new outbreaks of viral infections are reported from time to time despite the watchful eyes of World Health Organization (WHO). Consequently, scientists and researchers worldwide have put their combined efforts to understand the etiology, general biochemistry, genetic architecture, pathogenicity and the overall mechanism of infections caused by these viruses. Special interest was drawn to the viruses of new variants and subtypes. Studies are conducted to identify targets and develop strategies for possible intervention of these infectious diseases⁵. In the last century the most well documented pandemic is “**Spanish flu**”. This flu which was caused by a variant of avian influenza virus killed nearly 25 million people over a period of ~3 years (1918-1920)⁶⁻⁸. Some estimates even put the figure at 50-100 million which accounts to 3% of world population at that time. This still remains as the worst human disaster and often described as the “*greatest medical holocaust in human history*”. The present review provides an overview of some well and some not so well described viruses with particular reference to their pathogenic behavior, biochemistry, physiology as well as the currently available treatment options. *In addition, the functional roles played by the host cellular proteases in the infection process are highlighted.*

Virus

A virus is a tiny infectious organism which is much smaller than a fungus or bacterium. It invades a host living cell to reproduce (replicate) using its cellular machinery. The virus attaches to the surface of the host cell, penetrates and then releases its genetic materials and contents including the DNA and RNA inside the cell. The virus's DNA or RNA constitutes the most important genetic material containing all the information and machinery needed to replicate the virus. The genetic material of the virus takes control of the cell and forces it to replicate the virus. Usually the infected cell succumbs to death because the virus keeps it from performing its own normal functions. When it dies, the cell releases new viruses, which go on to infect other cells⁹.

Intervention strategies

Extensive research has led to the identification, structural and biochemical characterization of most viruses

and their genomes. The genome sequence and various characteristic domains with their functions have also been characterized. This has helped to develop strong antiviral agents for treatment and vaccination for prevention opportunities. But unfortunately in many cases all including the vaccine strategy met with limited success. The situation is more complicated by the ongoing mutations and modifications of most of these viruses, leading to their changed life cycle and virulence properties. It was generally accepted that the viral infections can be managed by targeting any one of the three major pathways. These are (i) *viral entry*, (ii) *integration of the viral DNA into the host cell genome* and (iii) *virus particle maturation*. Agents that interrupt any of these phases will have therapeutic potential. However, as mentioned earlier, in some cases none of these targets were able to deliver effective treatments although a few antiviral agents have been developed, which can effectively slow down the viral progression and spread¹⁰. Therefore, alternate targets and treatments are still required for even more effective therapeutic intervention of viral pathogenesis. This may include a combinatorial approach where the host enzyme/s that plays a significant and crucial role in the initiation and spread of viral infections in humans may also be targeted.

Host enzyme/s : Role in crucial viral glycoprotein processing

Research has revealed that many viral infections mediate via their surface coat glycoproteins also known as “**envelope**” glycoprotein. These membrane-bound viral glycoproteins are heavily glycosylated via specific Asparagine residues (Asn or “N” as presented by a single letter code) and often contain several disulphide bridges (involving Cys or “C” residues) conferring a specific conformation to the molecule. These glycoproteins that belong to class I fusion protein need to be activated via cleavage by one or more host cellular proteolytic enzymes (also called proteases) at selected sites giving rise to two fragments which take part in viral infection process. One fragment (usually the N-terminal piece) is then recognized by the host cell receptor while the other part undergoes conformation and structural modifications via interaction of its own two specific domains known as Hepta Repeat N-terminal (**HR-N**) and Hepta Repeat C-terminal (**HR-C**). This interaction takes place only after the cleavage. It then adopts a coiled-coil structure that bind to each other forming a 6-helix bundle which creates a passage for the virus particle to get entry into the host

cell. It then uses the host cell machinery to replicate and create a new virus particle which buds out of the cell. This process continues leading to the spread of the virus within the host system¹¹⁻¹³. To illustrate the significance of host enzyme furin in viral pathogenesis and its progression, the biochemistry of a few key viral infections are discussed in the sections below. It may be pointed out that furin processing of viral proproteins is the characteristic features of papilloma, corona, influenza or HN (**Hemagglutinin-Neuraminidase**) type viruses.

HIV AIDS : A typical example is the processing of HIV surface envelop coat glycoprotein GP160 into GP120 and GP41 by the host cellular enzyme “**furin**”, now called by the acronym as **PCSK3** with its structure and characteristic domains shown schematically in Fig. 1. The cleavage occurs at the position **Arg-Glu-Lys-Arg⁵¹¹ ↓Ala-Val-Gly (REKR⁵¹¹ ↓AVG)**¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Furin¹⁷ is the third member of Ca^{2+} -dependent mammalian subtilase superfamily called **Protein Convertases (PCs) or Proprotein Convertase**

Fig. 1. Proteolytic maturation of surface glycoprotein GP160 of HIV by host cellular convertase furin enzyme is depicted in this figure. The two heptad repeat domains at the N and C-terminal of gp41 [called as HR-N (residues 546-579) and HR-C (residues 624-666) peptides respectively] are shown in the figure, while gp120 and gp41 are shown as two separate fragments at the bottom of the figure on the left and right sides respectively. The known furin cleavage site at **KRRVVQREKR⁵¹¹ ↓ AV** is indicated in the figure. Disulfide bridges involving Cys residues are shown by connecting lines with positions as indicated within each domain. N-Glycosylation sites (22 within gp120 fragment) and (7 in membrane anchored gp41 fragment) are indicated by thick solid vertical lines at the bottom. The interaction between HR-N and HR-C domains is indicated by a curve thick white line. TM = Transmembrane domain, SP = Signal peptide, ER = Endoplasmic reticulum.

Subtilisin Kexins (PCSKs)¹⁸. Furin is ubiquitously expressed in varying levels in all cell and tissue types including the lung, which is considered as the port of viral entry into the host. **As a result, furin is involved in the cascade of events leading to the fusion of virions with the host cell membrane and may, therefore, be an alternate target for intervention of HIV AIDS.** In fact furin-specific inhibitors have been shown to inhibit HIV-virus spread and replication in a dose-dependent manner in cell culture experiments thereby providing necessary credibility to the above notion^{14,15}. Such inhibitory agents may find possible therapeutic applications in the intervention of HIV-pathogenesis. However such an innovative approach faces an enormous challenge and limitation in view of the fact that furin activity is required to support many of life’s vital processes and events related to health and metabolism.

SARS-corona virus : Furin is also implicated in SARS corona virus infection where it plays a significant role in cleaving SARS-corona virus glycoprotein known as “**Spike or S**” protein at **RNTR⁷⁶¹ ↓EV** site leading to two fragments namely the N-terminal soluble S1 and C-terminal membrane bound S2 forms which respectively play important roles in viral recognition by the host cell receptor and fusiogenic process involving the host cell (Fig. 2). Three-dimensional crystal structure revealed that following the cleavage, the fragment S2 assumes a typical 6-

Fig. 2. Schematic presentation of 1255 amino acid long surface S (spike) glycoprotein of human SARS corona virus with characteristic domains is presented in this figure. The two fragments formed (S1 and S2) following proteolytic cleavage by host cellular convertase furin enzyme, then play crucial role in viral recognition, fusion and replication process. The two hepta repeat (HR1 and HR2) domains of S2 fragment interact with each other to create a coiled-coil structure that helps in viral fusion whereas S1 is recognized by the host cell surface receptor.

helix bundle structure involving its HR-N and HR-C domains which interact with one another. This ultimately allows it to slowly get internalized into the host cell. Thus, here again the host enzyme furin is involved in mediating the pathogenesis and infection caused by SARS corona virus¹⁹⁻²².

Influenza-A virus : H5N1, H1N1 and other new hybrid types : H5N1 and H1N1 are subtypes of common cold influenza-A virus. These are respectively known as Swine flu and Hong Kong influenza virus respectively. The surface glycoproteins of these viruses are composed of two types of protein antigens called **Hemagglutinin (H)** and **Neuraminidase (N)** and consequently they are termed as **HN** type viruses. There are 16 and 9 different types of Hemagglutinin (H1 to H16) and Neuraminidase (N1 to N9). There are 23 known H-N associations out of 135 potential ones. Of these 15 are found in avian (birds). A slight modification or change in recombination of viruses of different lineages is sufficient to create new and potentially of more virulent strains. The pathogenicity of a particular HN strain virus depends on the ability of hemagglutinin to cleave into two fragments required for the virus to enter into the cell.

Among the various HN type viruses, **H5N1** (Hong Kong or Bird flu) and more recently **H1N1** (which originated from “Swine flu”) and a few other new strains were found to be extremely virulent. It is now nearly established that the H (hemagglutinin) proteins of these viruses are cleaved by the host cellular protease/s of PCSK-family such as furin, leading to their activation and subsequent infection of the host cell. In fact, all these proteins contain the highly basic **Arg-X-Arg/Lys-Arg↓ (R-X-R/K-R↓)** (X = any amino acid, vertical arrow indicates the cleavage site) sequence at the cleavage site which is consistent with the recognition motif of furin and other PC-enzymes¹⁸. The cleavage sites of HA proteins of H5N1, H1N1 and other hybrid subtypes that are either proposed or confirmed are indicated in Fig. 3. It is likely and feared that the newer strain derived from HA proteins may be cleaved at much faster kinetics by the PCSK enzymes such as furin leading to their high virulence. In fact, it was revealed that the HA protein of H5N1, which contains an insertion of an additional tetrapeptide unit namely “**RERR**” as a result of mutation near the cleavage site, makes it ~ 100 times more easily

Fig. 3. Schematic presentation of HA (hemagglutinin) proteins of H5N1, H1N1 with indicated furin cleavage sites. The potential new hybrid type of HN (hemagglutinin neuraminidase) viral glycoprotein derived from H5N1 and H1N1 is shown at the bottom of the figure.

cleaved by furin at least in *in vitro* condition and this explains its high virulence and infectivity potential¹¹.

Chikungunya virus : This virus is transmitted via mosquito bites and is relatively rare until recent years. Its entire genome, shown in Fig. 4, codes several key proteins but among them the structural protein comprising the domains “**E3-E2**” has drawn considerable research interest because of its crucial role in infection process.

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of Asian Chikungunya virus genome protein sequence showing the critical cleavage site between E2 and E3 domains that contains a specific PC-or furin enzyme cleavage motif. Various other regions within structural and nonstructural domains along with some non mutations observed mainly in the cerebrospinal fluid are also indicated in the figure. The total length of the structural protein is either 1241 or 1248 amino acids, whereas the nonstructural protein is 2474 amino acid long.

This surface viral fusion protein has been shown to be cleaved by the PCSK-enzyme furin, leading to two fragments E3 and E2 which then take part in the various steps of viral fusion and pathogenesis²³. Application of furin inhibitor in *vero* cells infected with chikungunya virus significantly lowers the viral load and replication and this effect has been shown to be dose-dependent²⁴. This observation further confirms the key role played by the host enzyme furin in virus : host-membrane interaction and fusion leading to infection. Similar studies have also been conducted with furin inhibitors against other viral diseases with similar results providing additional evidence in favor of the importance of host enzyme furin in infections caused by the above viruses.

Conformational features of furin processing sites of viral glycoproteins

Owing to the critical importance of the membrane-bound host enzyme furin which mediates the cleavages of viral glycoproteins prior to fusion, it is considered likely that the viral glycoproteins may possess membrane binding or interacting property and this may occur near its cleavage domain. It is interesting to point out that each cleavage site is characterized by the presence of highly polar **Arg/Lys-X-Arg/Lys-Arg** tetrapeptide sequence motif just prior to the cleavage site. Such sequence motif has already been characterized as the one most recognized by furin²⁵. In order to demonstrate this and also to examine the nature of amino acids in surrounding regions, a 30-mer peptide sequence with 15 amino acids on either side of the cleavage was designed from each of the viral glycoproteins, as discussed above. We selected the 30-mer size as arbitrary which constitutes a reasonably large peptide so as to exhibit a secondary structure. The list with the amino acid sequence of various viral peptides analysed in this study is shown in Table 3. In order to investigate the secondary structural feature, particularly amphipathic helix (known for its membrane binding activity) around the cleavage site, we performed helix analysis on all the 19 viral peptides encompassing the cleavage site as indicated in Table 3. For this analysis study, we used the software program HELIQUEST developed by Gauthier *et al.*²⁶ available at the web address www.heliquest.lpmc.cnrs.fr. For each analysed peptide, we calculated their physicochemical parameter values such as **mean Hydrophobicity (H)**, **Hydrophobic moment**

(μ H), **Net charge (NT)** and determined the presence, if any, of hydrophobic face (**HF**) and sequence. The results are depicted in column 3 in Table 4. It is quite clear that 9 out of 19 peptides tested showed the presence of an amphipathic helix with minimum number of charged or polar residues on one side and hydrophobic residues of minimum length on the other side^{27,28}. The peptide segment constituting the hydrophobic face ranges from the required minimum of three amino acids (e.g. *Leu-Tyr-Ile* for Chikungunya Nagpur strain; *Pro-Ala-Ala* for Mumps; *Val-Gly-Leu* for Respiratory syncytial and *Ile-Met-Val* for SARS corona virus peptides) to the heptapeptide *Val-Val-Val-Ala-La-Leu-Val* and *Ala-Phe-Ala-Val-Leu-Pro-Gly* for T-Cell Leukemia and HIV-1 peptides, respectively (see Fig. 5 for their amphipathic wheel diagrams). It is interesting to note that those viral peptides that contain the amphipathic helices are known to be cleaved quite efficiently by the the host protease furin and these viruses also exhibit increased virulence compared to the other viruses that lack amphipathic helix in their 30-peptides. This finding is very interesting, significant and novel. **It may well represent a signature of structure that contributes to the observed increased cleavage by host protease furin leading to higher degree of virulence properties.** Whether it constitutes as a common general feature for higher degree of cleavage by furin for any viral glycoprotein is not quite clear and may require additional work.

Predicted 3-dimensional structures of viral glycoprotein cleavage site domain

Besides the secondary structure analysis described above, we have also carried out 3-dimensional structure analysis of the above 30-mer viral peptides. This is intended to find the presence of any commonality in the backbone structure of the peptide segment bearing the furin cleavage site. Our findings were summarized in Table 4 while the model structures of a few key viral peptides were shown in Figs. 6–9 to highlight some of the important structural features. Clearly, in all the peptides modeled we noted at least one strong H-bonding prior to or at the furin cleavage site characterized by the sequence **Arg¹⁵-X** where X = any non-basic amino acid. It is further observed that in most cases the H-bonding occurs between the guandine side chain NH₂ of Arg residue and

Table 3. List of various viral envelope coat surface glycoproteins with their partial amino acid sequences showing the crucial cleavage site with key basic residues underlined for host cellular protease furin

List	Virus name	Name of surface glycoprotein	Amino acid sequence at the cleavage site	Accession number
1	Ebola (Mayinga Zaire)	gP	⁴⁸⁷ AGVAGLITGG <u>RRTRR</u> EAIVN AQPKCNP ⁵¹⁶	AAD14585 [30]
2	Ebola (Tai Forest)	gP	⁴⁸⁷ RGVTNLLTGS <u>RRKRR</u> DVTPN TQPKCNP ⁵¹⁶	YP_003815426 [31]
3	Ebola (Sudan, Nakisamata)	Structural gP	⁴⁸⁷ TGILGSLGLR <u>KRSRR</u> QTNTK ATGKC NPNLH ⁵¹⁶	AFP28231 [32]
4	Marburg (Kenya Musoke)	Glycoprotein gP	⁵⁴⁶ VLIKNQNNLV <u>CRLRR</u> LANQT AKSLE LLLRV ⁵⁷⁵	CAA78117 [33]
5	Chikungunya (Nagpur, India)	E3-E2 Structural coat protein	³¹¹ LLQASLTCSP <u>RQRR</u> SIKDN FNVYKATRPY ³⁴⁰ LAHCPDC	Q5WQY5 [34]
6	Chikungunya (S27 Africa)	E3-E2 Structural protein	³¹¹ LLQASLTCSP <u>HRQRR</u> STKDN FNVYKATRPY ³⁴⁰ LAHCPDC	Q8JUX5 [35]
7	hSARS corona (Urbani)	Spike fusion protein	⁷⁴⁶ RALSGIAAEQ <u>DRNTR</u> EVFAQ VKQMYKTPTL ⁷⁷⁵	CAL40866 [36]
8	Avian bronchitis (Beaudette)	gP	⁵²³ QFYIKITNGT <u>RRFRR</u> SITEN VANCYPVSYG ⁵⁵²	P11223 [37]
9	Dengue (Brazil/97/11)	prM protein	¹⁹¹ YGTCSTGEH <u>RRDKR</u> SVALA PHVGLGLETR ²²⁰	P27909 [38]
10	Epstein-Barr (B95-8) (Human herpes virus4)	gP	⁴¹⁷ ARGSTPAAVL <u>RRRRR</u> DAGNA TTPVPPTAPG ⁴⁴⁶	P03188 [39]
11	Human Immuno Deficiency-1	gP160	⁴⁹⁶ APT <u>KAKRR</u> VV <u>QREKR</u> AVGIG ALFLGFLGAA ⁵³⁵	P04578 [40]
12	Human Respiratory Syncytial (A2)	Fusion protein	¹²² AKKTNVTLSE <u>KRKRR</u> FLGFL LGVGSIAIASG ¹⁵¹	P03420 [41]
13	Human T-cell Leukemia		²⁹⁴ FSLAPVPPPA <u>TRRRR</u> AVPIA VWLVSALAAG ³²³	P03383 [42]
14	Mumps	F protein	⁹⁸ NNITSPSPGS <u>RRHKR</u> FAGIA IGIAALGVAT ¹¹⁷	AAL76265 [43]
15	Varicella Zoster	gP II	⁴⁸⁰ HSPQKHPTRN <u>TRSRR</u> SVPVE LRANRTITTT ⁵⁰⁹	Q4JR05 [44]
16	Yellow fever (polyprotein)	prM	¹⁹⁶ YGKCDASGRS <u>RRSRR</u> AIDLPTHENHGLKTR ²²⁵	ACU68590 [45]
17	Influenza-equine	Hemagglutinin	³³⁵ NSTHKQLTHH <u>MRKKR</u> GLFGA IAGFIENGWE ³⁶⁴	AAA00818 [46]
18	Human cytomegalo	gP	⁴⁴⁶ ANRSSLNLTH <u>NRTKR</u> STDGN NATHLSNMES ⁴⁷⁵	P13201 [47]
19	Hong Kong (H5N1)	Hemagglutinin H5	³³² GLRNTPQRE <u>RRKKR</u> GLFGA IAGFIEGGWQ ³⁶¹	AAC32101 [48]

Table 4. Characteristic structural features of 30-mer peptides of various glycoproteins in terms of hydrogen bonding based on 3-dimensional theoretical model structures (Hyperchem program) as well as hydrophobic contents based on amphipathic helix wheel structure based on Heliquest program (**H** = Mean Hydrophobicity; **μ H** = Hydrophobic moment; **NT** = Net charge; **HF** = Hydrophobic face showing amino acid sequence *in italics* if present. Note : The viral strains which exhibited amphipathic helix structure with high H and/or HM values and a defined HF with hydrophobic segment are indicated with underline

Viral strain	Position of hydrogen bonding	Important physicochemical parameters associated in amphipathic wheel diagram			
		H	μH	NT	HF
Avian Bronchitis	Arg 12 (NH ₂) - Phe 13 (C=O)	0.329	0.334	4	None
Beaudette	Arg 14 (NH ₂) - Arg 15 (C=O)				
Chikungunya Africa	Arg 14 (NH ₂) - Arg 15 (C=O)	0.20	0.16	5	None
Chikungunya, Nagpur	Arg 11 (NH ₂) - Arg 12 (C=O) Arg 11 (NH ₂) - Gln 13 (C=O)	0.213	0.216	6	<i>Leu-Tyr-Ile</i>
Dengue, Brazil	Arg 11 (NH ₂) - Arg 12 (C=O) Arg 12 (NH ₂) - Asp 13 (C=O)	0.0168	0.029	2	None
Ebola, Sudan	Arg 15 (NH ₂) - Lys 16 (C=O) Arg 17 (NH ₂) - Ser 18 (C=O)	0.108	0.119	7	None
Ebola, Zaire	Arg 12 (NH ₂) - Thr 13 (C=O) Arg 14 (NH ₂) - Arg 15 (C=O)	0.221	0.163	4	None
Ebola, Tai Forest	Arg 11 (NH ₂) - Arg 12 (C=O) Arg 12 (NH ₂) - Lys 13 (C=O)	0.065	0.205	6	None
Epstein Barr (Herpes)	Arg 2 (NH ₂) - Gly 3 (C=O) Arg 15 (NH ₂) - Asp 16 (C=O) Thr 22 (NH ₂) - Pro 23 (C=O)	0.106	0.121	5	<i>Pro-Val-Ala-Leu-Ala</i>
Human Cytomegalo	Asn 7 (C=O) - Thr 9 (OH) Asn 21 (C=O) - Ala 22 (NH ₂) Thr 23 (OH) - His 24 (C=O) His 24 (N) - Leu 25 (NH ₂)	-0.033	0.067	2	None
HIV-1	Arg 12 (NH₂) - Glu 13 (C=O)	0.304	0.220	6	<i>Ala-Phe-Ala-Val-Leu-Pro-Gly</i>
Influenza (Type A)	His 9 (NH ₂) - His 9 (NH ₂)	0.262	0.414	3	<i>Leu-Ile-Phe-Met-Trp</i>
Equine	Arg 15 (NH ₂) - Gly 16 (C=O)				
T-cell Leukemia	Arg 15 (NH₂) - Gly 16 (C=O)	0.591	0.05	4	<i>Val-Val-Val-Ala-Ala-Leu-Val</i>
Marburg	Asn 7 (NH ₂) - Arg 11 (N)	0.398	0.427	5	<i>Ala-Val-Leu-Ile-Ala</i>
Mumps	Thr 4 (OH) - Ser 5 (C=O) Arg 11 (NH ₂) - Arg 12 (C=O) Arg 12 (NH ₂) - His 13 (C=O) Arg 15 (H) - Phe 16 (C=O)	0.340	0.087	4	<i>Pro-Ala-Ala</i>
Respiratory Syncytial	Arg 15 (NH ₂) - Phe 16 (C=O)	0.246	0.20	8	<i>Val-Gly-Leu</i>
SARS	Arg 12 (NH ₂) - Asn 13 (C=O)	0.20	0.341	2	<i>Ile-Met-Val</i>
Varicella Zoster	Arg 14 (NH ₂) - Arg 15 (C=O) Arg 15 (NH ₂) - Ser 16 (C=O) Arg 25 (NH ₂) - Thr 26 (C=O) Thr 28 (OH) - Thr 29 (C=O)	0.033	0.079	6	None
Yellow Fever	Arg 11 (NH ₂) - Arg 12 (C=O) Arg 12 (NH ₂) - Ser 13 (C=O)	-0.037	0.058	5	None
Hong Kong (H5N1)	Arg 12 (H) - Lys 13 (C=O)	0.184	0.205	6	<i>Pro-Phe-Ala-Leu</i>

Fig. 5. Amphipathic helix diagram of 30-mer viral peptides derived from Human T-Cell Leukemia and Human Immuno Deficiency virus glycoproteins. Both peptides contain the furin cleavage site precisely in the midpoint.

the amide or side chain carbonyl/amino groups of the amino acid residue located near the post cleavage site. All molecular modelings were obtained by using Pollok-Robillard energy minimization calculation based on HYPERCHEM-version 8 software program. Figs. 7-9 show the presence of H-bonds in four representative viral peptide models derived from HIV-1, Human T-Cell Leu-

kemia, Varicella-Zoster and Marburg glyco- or fusion proteins. Such H-bonds, as shown in the figures, expose the scissile peptide bond more in a manner so as to be highly accessible to the host cellular enzyme furin for cleavage.

We also observed that upon insertion of tetrapeptide RERR sequence, as found in the highly virulent H5N1 strain of influenza virus, the resulting peptide adopted a structure with much improved amphipathic character which might be linked to the observed increased cleavage efficiency by furin. This is an important and highly significant observation despite the fact that the above conclusion was obtained through theoretical computational analysis²⁹ performed *in vacuo* using hyperchem software programs (v 8.0) available from Hypercube Inc (<http://www.hyper.com/?tabid=360>). However, this predicted structural finding for the peptide region consisting of cleavage site by the host enzyme deserves a careful scrutiny, examination as well as further work in future.

Host enzyme as potential target for viral intervention

The above sections clearly suggested that the host cellular protease particularly the convertase furin is crucial for viral spread and pathogenesis, owing to its ability to cleave and activate viral surface glycoproteins. Interestingly, most of the known highly virulent viruses possess glycoproteins that contain a sequence motif at the cleavage site consistent with that recognized by furin and other PCSK enzymes (Table 3). Therefore, it is expected that reducing its protease activity by using specific inhibitors may provide an alternate intervention strategy for viral intervention. In fact, several studies have confirmed the anti-viral properties of furin inhibitors at least *in vitro* and *ex vivo* cellular models. However, inhibiting furin activity using specific inhibitors for intervention of viral infections may not be that simple since furin activity is vital for normal physiological function, development and metabolism. Therefore, shutting down overall furin activity may lead to serious consequences and side effects. However, one can circumvent this challenge by developing cell impermeable inhibitors of furin^{24,25} which will only target furin present at the cell surface or in extracellular environment but not the intracellular furin. Moreover, furin inhibitors may be applied in an organ-specific manner. For example it can be used as a nasal spray

Fig. 6. Theoretical 3-dimensional model structure of 30-mer HIV-1 gp160 (496-525) peptide encompassing the crucial furin cleavage side (as indicated by an arrow) is shown in the figure. The sequence of the peptide is also shown while the H-bond was displayed by a dotted line in the expanded part of the model figure (lower panel). The molecular modeling was performed by using energy Pollok-Robillard energy minimization calculation in Hyperchem software programs.

Fig. 7. Theoretical 3-dimensional model structure of 30-mer Human T-Cell Leukemia (294-323) peptide encompassing the crucial furin cleavage side (as indicated by an arrow) is shown in the figure. The sequence of the peptide is also indicated while the H-bond was displayed by a dotted line in the expanded part of the model figure (lower panel). The molecular modeling was performed as described in Fig. 6.

Fig. 8. Theoretical 3-dimensional model structure of 30-mer Varicella Zoster gp (480-509) peptide encompassing the crucial furin cleavage side (as indicated by an arrow) is shown in the figure. The sequence of the peptide is also indicated while the H-bonds (2 in this case) were displayed by dotted lines in the expanded parts of the model figure (lower panels). The molecular modeling was performed as described in Fig. 6.

Fig. 9. Theoretical 3-dimensional model structure of 30-mer Marburg (Kenya) gp (546-575) peptide encompassing the crucial furin cleavage side (as indicated by an arrow) is shown in the figure. The sequence of the peptide is also indicated while the H-bonds (2 in this case) were displayed by dotted lines in the expanded parts of the model figure (lower panels). The molecular modeling was performed as described in Fig. 6.

which will then target only the lung – the major entry point of most viruses particularly those of respiratory type.

Summary and conclusion

The above review confirmed the important and crucial role of host enzymes such as furin in viral infections. Thus it can be possible to use inhibitors (particularly those which do not cross the cell membrane) of furin as potential therapeutic agents to arrest the spread of viral infection and pathogenesis as long as they are delivered in an organ-specific manner. These inhibitors can be well used either alone or in combination with other antiviral agents that target the viral protease or components. More research should be encouraged to develop small molecule and highly selective inhibitors to furin that are cell impermeable as possible agents for blockade of viral infection.

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Abbreviations

aa = Amino acid, AIDS = Acquired Immuno Deficiency Syndrome, HA = Hemagglutinin, HIV = Human immunodeficiency virus, HN = Hemagglutinin Neuraminidase, HR = Hepta Repeat, HR-C = Hepta Repeat C-terminal, HR-N = Hepta Repeat N-terminal, N = Neuraminidase, PC = Proprotein Convertase, hSARS = Human Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, S protein = Spike protein.

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